

Metal Ion Interaction with some Antibiotic Drugs of Penicillin Family. Part-I. Equilibrium Study on the Complex Formation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with 6-Aminopenicillanic Acid

G. N. MUKHERJEE*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 039
and

T. K. GHOSH

Department of Chemistry, R. K. Mission Vivekananda Centenary College, Rahara, 24-Parganas (North)

Manuscript received 20 May 1990, revised 22 March 1991, accepted 8 April 1991

Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric study on the interaction of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn) with 6-aminopenicillanic acid (LH^{\pm}) has provided evidence of formation of only 1:1 metal-ligand complexes, ML^+ , $ML(OH)$ and $ML(OH)_2$. Formation constants of the complexes were determined at 37° in aqueous solution having a fixed ionic strength ($0.1 M NaNO_3$) and correlated with the modes of bonding of the ligand, π -electron delocalisation and steric crowding in such complexes

PENICILLIN group of antibiotic drugs are known to inhibit protein synthesis in bacteria by causing misreading of the genetic code¹. Enzymes responsible for genetic information transfer require one or other of the biological metal ions for their reactivity and also for their structural integrity²⁻⁴. Metal ions by their kind or by their concentration or by both, may influence the conformation of the ribosome, where the protein synthesis takes place. Due to lack of our knowledge about the interaction of the antibiotic drugs with metal ions and the influence thereto of the amino acids, small peptides, nucleic bases, nucleosides and nucleotides, the literature is silent about the specific inhibitory roles played by these drugs to the protein synthesis. Therefore, a systematic investigation on the interaction of biological metal ions with antibiotic drugs of the penicillin family in the absence and in the presence of the above biological ligands is planned to throw some light upon the molecular mechanisms of action of these drugs. The present paper describes an equilibrium study on the interaction of 6-aminopenicillanic acid (hereafter, 6-APA, or LH^{\pm}) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in aqueous solution at a fixed ionic strength ($I=0.1 M NaNO_3$) at $37 \pm 0.1^{\circ}$.

Experimental

The ligand, 6-APA was of A.R. grade (Sigma). Solutions of other reagents (A.R. quality) were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water. Metal nitrate solutions were standardised by ion-exchange separation combined with acid-base and complexo-

Fig. 1. pH titration curves of 6-APA in the absence and in presence of metal ions in aqueous solution of ionic strength, $I=0.1 M (NaNO_3)$ at $37 \pm 0.1^{\circ}$: curves (1), $0.005 M HNO_3$; (2), (1)+ $0.001 M Cu(NO_3)_2$; (3), (1)+ $0.001 M Zn(NO_3)_2$; (4), (1)+ $0.001 M Ni(NO_3)_2$; (5), (1)+ $0.001 M Co(NO_3)_2$; (6), $0.01 M HNO_3 + 0.005 M$ 6-APA (LH^{\pm}); (7), (6)+ $0.001 M Cu(NO_3)_2$; (8), (6)+ $0.001 M Zn(NO_3)_2$; (9), (6)+ $0.001 M Ni(NO_3)_2$; (10), (6)+ $0.001 M Co(NO_3)_2$; titrant: $0.1 M NaOH$, initial volume = 25 ml.

metric titrations⁵. Carbonate-free NaOH solution⁶ was used as the titrant.

pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) employing a glass electrode in conjunction with a SCE. The following solutions were prepared for the pH-metric study: (i), 0.005 M HNO₃; (ii), (i) + 0.001–0.002 M metal nitrate; (iii), 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.005 M 6-APA in the form of LH₂⁺; (iv), (iii) + 0.001–0.002 M metal nitrate. Initial volume of each solution was 25 ml. The required amount of NaNO₃ was placed in each solution to have a fixed ionic strength, $I=0.1$ M. All the solutions were allowed to attain equilibrium at $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$ (thermostated) and titrated with standard 0.1 M NaOH having the desired ionic strength and maintained at the same temperature. A representative set of pH-titration data are presented in Fig. 1. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were evaluated by running the programme SCOGS⁷ with the aid of a PC-XT computer system. Preliminary estimates of some of the constants supplied to the computer as input data were evaluated by analysing the pH-titration curves according to the procedure of Irving and Rossotti⁸. Computer refined values of the formation constants are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH 6-APA

Temp. = $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $I=0.1$ M (NaNO₃)

Constant	H ⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
$pK_{LH_2}^H$	1.82	—	—	—	—
pK_{LH}^H	4.84	—	—	—	—
pK_M^H	—	8.21	8.05	6.29	7.84
pK_M^{2H}	—	17.29	16.83	13.05	14.87
$\log K_{ML}^M$	—	3.13	3.30	4.10	1.90
$\log K_{(M+LH)}^H$	—	-1.71	-1.54	-0.74	-2.94
$\log \beta_{(M+L)}^H$	—	-6.80	-6.32	-3.20	-8.83
$\log \beta_{(M+L)}^{2H}$	—	—	—	-14.50	—
$pK_{ML(H_2O)_2}^H$	—	9.93	9.62	7.30	10.23
$pK_{ML(OH)(H_2O)}^H$	—	—	—	11.30	—

Limits of error in the constants = ± 0.02 in log units.

Results and Discussion

The ligand 6-APA (1) being a strong acid (LH) exists as a zwitterionic species, LH[±] (2)⁹.

For this reason it is appreciably soluble in water. The protonated form (LH₂⁺) is titrated as a biprotic acid and offered two buffer regions between pH (1–2.5) and (3–5), obviously due to successive deprotonation of the COOH and the NH₃⁺ moieties respectively.

Complex formation of 6-APA with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ion was observed at pH ≥ 3 , where the ligand was predominantly in the LH[±] form. Complex formation with Cu^{II} was associated with a series of colour changes on the increase of pH. At pH ~ 3.5 ($\bar{n} \approx 1$), Cu^{II}–6-APA solution had a light green colour ($\lambda_{\max} = 720$ nm) which changed to reddish brown ($\lambda_{\max} = 570$ nm) at pH ~ 9 ($\bar{n} > 2$) where, \bar{n} stands for the average number of protons⁸ released due to the reaction of M²⁺ ions with LH[±]. On further increase of pH the solution turned yellow ($\lambda_{\max} = 675$ nm) at pH ≈ 11 ($\bar{n} \approx 3$). The resulting solution on standing for several days gradually turned intense violet. Mole-ratio study of Cu^{II}–6-APA mixtures at pH values corresponding to $\bar{n} = 1, 2$ and 3 gave only 1 : 1 Cu^{II}–6-APA complexes. Therefore, complexes higher than 1 : 1 were excluded from the calculation of metal-ligand constants. Buffer regions corresponding to metal-ligand complexation equilibria were observed (Fig. 1) at pH values much lower than those of the hydrolytic equilibria of M²⁺ (aq.) ions. Therefore, simple hydroxo species were less likely to occur. However, at higher pH values the occurrence of ternary metal-ligand hydroxo complexes could not be ruled out. Therefore, the species LH[±], L⁻, Cu²⁺, CuL⁺, CuL(OH) and CuL(OH)₂⁻ were considered in calculating the metal-ligand constants.

From the distribution profiles of Cu²⁺ and LH[±] ions (Fig. 2) it appeared that the complex CuL⁺ was formed according to the equilibria,

$$K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}} = \frac{[\text{CuL}]}{[\text{Cu}][\text{L}]} \quad (1)$$

which involved substitution of the NH₃⁺ proton of the ligand by Cu^{II} ion. The observed λ_{\max} (720 nm) of the Cu^{II}–6-APA mixture at $\bar{n} = 1$ (pH ≈ 3.5) was close to the calculated value (740 nm) for a square-planar copper complex in which the Cu^{II} ion is coordinated by an amino-nitrogen atom, a carbonyl-oxygen atom and two H₂O molecules¹⁰. It was, therefore, obvious that Cu^{II} ion in the CuL⁺ complex was coordinated by the 6-amino-nitrogen atom and 7-carbonyl-oxygen atom of the ligand and took up two molecules of solvent water to have a square-planar geometry (3). The ternary hydroxo complexes CuL(OH) and CuL(OH)₂⁻, therefore, resulted from deprotonation of these coordinated water molecules in this CuL(H₂O)₂[±] complex according to equilibria (2) and (3)

$$K_{\text{CuL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2}^{\text{H}} = \frac{[\text{CuL}(\text{OH})][\text{H}^{+}]}{[\text{CuL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^{\pm}]} \quad (2)$$

$$K_{\text{CuL}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})}^{\text{H}} = \frac{[\text{CuL}(\text{OH})_2^{-}][\text{H}^{+}]}{[\text{CuL}(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Cu^{II}-6-APA equilibria.

The change in colour of the metal-ligand solution in going from $\bar{n}=1$ to higher values indicated a remarkable change of ligand field strength around the metal ion. A very likely possibility could be a structural change from a Cu[(N)(O)₃] system as in 3 to a Cu[(N)(S)(O)₃] system as in 4 according to eqm. (4), involving the substitution of carbonyl oxygen atom by the ring sulphur atom of the ligand.

$$K_{CuL(H_2O)_2}^{2H} = K_{CuL(H_2O)_2}^H \times K_{CuL(OH)(H_2O)}^H \quad (4)$$

$$= ([H]^2[4])/[3]$$

Extensive π -electron delocalisation from the Cu^{II} ion to the vacant $d\pi$ orbitals of S-donor atom in structure 4 possibly served as the driving force that led to the deprotonation of the two coordinated water molecules in the CuL(H₂O)₂⁺ complex.

Complex formation of 6-APA with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} ions were observed at pH values slightly higher than those with Cu^{II} ion. It was, however, evident from the complex distribution curves of these systems that the complex formation equilibria of 6-APA with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} were similar to those with Cu^{II} ion. The only difference was that the dihydroxo species, ML(OH)₂ were formed in so negligible amounts that they could not even be identified in the species distribution curves. Interestingly, there was no change of colour of Co^{II} or Ni^{II} solution in

the presence of 6-APA with rise of pH. This was possibly due to lower affinity of these metal ions for the sulphur donor atom as compared to that of Cu^{II}. Thus, non-existence of the structural equilibria (4) for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and possibly for Zn^{II} might be the reason for the absence of dihydroxo species ML(OH)₂ for these metal ions. Concentrations of free M²⁺ ions in the entire pH range with all the M²⁺-6-APA equilibria were insufficient to exceed the solubility products of the metal hydroxides. Steric hindrance by the methyl groups at position-2 might be responsible for the non-existence of complexes higher than 1 : 1 with all these metal ions.

Acknowledgement

Authors' extreme indebtedness are due to Swami Satya Priyanandaji Maharaj, Vice-Principal, R. K. Mission Vivekananda Centenary College, Rahara, for his kind interest in this work.

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